

FUEL CELL HYBRID VEHICLES AND THEIR ROLE IN THE DECARBONISATION OF ROAD TRANSPORT

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Abstract

Nearly ten years have passed since the comeback of battery electric vehicles (BEVs). However, the percentage of such vehicles on the roads is still low and there is widespread concern about the long-term success of this technology. On the other hand, vehicles fueled with hydrogen, which it is beginning to be praised by several car companies as the fuel of future, do not yet have broad market acceptance, being even lower than battery electric vehicles and facing significant barriers for a widespread diffusion. A novel type-approval test procedure is developed aiming to establish an impartial simulation-based comparative analysis of technical feasibility, performance, range, and greenhouse gas emissions of two powertrains that manage electricity stored in a lithium-ion battery and hydrogen in tanks: Plug-In Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicle (FC-PHEV) and Extended Range Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicle (FC-EREV). The model considers the barriers and how to avoid them through the implementation of a set of fuel management rules. The findings indicate that hybridization achieves greater ranges and lower greenhouse gas emissions, opening the door to introduce these vehicles onto the market without the need to wait till the main barrier, the hydrogen refueling infrastructure, is fully developed.

Highlights

- Current situation on battery electric vehicle and fuel cell vehicles are analyzed.
- The need to develop a hybrid powertrain with battery and hydrogen is justified.
- Two proposals of powertrain for hydrogen-electricity hybrids are presented. A set of fuel management rules is designed.

- A new type-approval test procedure is defined to measure consumption and emissions of two powertrain proposals
- An extensive simulation campaign is conducted, which shows positive results about the viability of the proposed powertrains

Keywords: Hydrogen; Fuel cell; Hybrid vehicles; Emissions; Type-approval test procedure

1. INTRODUCTION

Global warming and poor air quality in urban areas are two driving factors moving our society towards the electrification of road transport¹, especially in large urban areas. The world population has been growing continuously since 1950, in the same way that global urbanization. Since 2007, over 50% of the global population lives in urban areas (Seto et al, 2014). In 2014 there were 28 mega-cities², accumulating 453 million residents (12% of the global population), the figure was increased to 38 in 2019 and it is expected that in 2030 there will be 41 megacities (Demographia, 2019). This phenomenon is also happening in large cities (5 million-10 million inhabitants), medium-sized cities (1 million-5 million inhabitants), and small cities (500,000 - 1 million inhabitants). The inherent problem, among others, is the increase in people and goods transportation and the potential adverse impact in pollutant emissions expected. Every day, hundreds of media from around the world echo the recognition of the complex problem of air quality and global warming and that it will require a change of mindset leading to a level of international cooperation that has not yet been seen. However, although there have been changes in what governments do, the figures are truly staggering: 1) from 2000 to 2019 the number of manufactured passenger vehicles worldwide has grown from 41.22 million to 70.47 million per year (IEA, 2019); 2) China is the leading country in terms of passenger car production with around 21.4 million units. This compares to about 8.3 million units in Japan (OICA, 2020); 3) Markets are not yet saturated, as it is reflected by the car density indicator (number of motor vehicles per 1000 inhabitants) in the highest markets as China (173), the European Union (602) and United States (811); 4) China remained the top light vehicle

¹ Globally, road transport is responsible for about 16% of man-made CO₂ emissions (OICA, 2019)

² A city and/or metropolitan area with a very high population of at least 10 million. Tokyo, New York or Seoul are examples of mega-cities.

producing country since 2019. Japan, Germany, India, and South Korea complete the list of the world's largest car producers and 5) global electric car sales were close to 2 million in 2018 (less than 2.7 % share), more than two-thirds of these electric car sales were Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs), therefore there exist a great market opportunity based on the electric vehicle adoption. These are the key discussion points about the transition towards a new and cleaner mobility scenario (Shafiei et al., 2017). The confluence of these information shows that the production and sales of passenger vehicles are expected to continue rising and the transition to electric propulsion is a fact, but it is taking place relatively slowly and, from an environmental point of view, insufficient. In this paper, the authors discuss the barriers that are slowing down the transition towards electrified mobility and the environmental effects of a new type of hybrid electric vehicle, powered by hydrogen and a fuel cell, in the context of sustainable mobility. Firstly, through the assessment of their specific environmental impact. Secondly, through the explanation of the methodology applied. Thirdly, through the discussion of implications of a potential widespread expansion of the use of these powertrains.

1.1 Battery electric vehicle: a present with a bleak future

Battery electric vehicles have been increasing their presence in the automobile market slowly but tireless since 2010³ and now, in 2021, everything suggests that they will play an important role in reducing the climate impact of transport as well as local air pollution to reach carbon-neutral mobility. Nevertheless, there are still some well-known barriers that have prevented their massive adoption (Junquera et al., 2016). These barriers have been overcome in some territories. Norway is an example (Haugneland et al., 2016) where the battery electric vehicle has been early and successfully adopted. But, when studying the big picture, the trend is not encouraging. The European Union, with a fleet of 270 million passenger cars, barely reaches 0.2% of the global fleet (EAFO, 2020). The aforementioned barriers are mainly the range (cause of the range anxiety), the retail price of the vehicle, the battery refill time, and the absence of charging infrastructure. In addition to the retail price, the lack of available recharging infrastructure represents the second biggest hurdle for consumers to opt for an electric car. However, a study by Bloomberg New Energy Finance (2019) reveals that the third part of vehicles in the world will be powered by electricity by the year

³ In January 2017, cumulative global sales of electric vehicles reached the second million milestone. Lutsey (2017)

2040. In fact, the automotive industry has taken long time to move forward, but at least it has decided to solve the barriers by developing a strategic plan based on the following points: a) including higher capacity battery packs. The top selling BEVs (Nissan Leaf, Renault Zoe or BMW i3) have increased their electricity storage capacity and estimated range. Nissan Leaf boosted its battery storage capacity from 24 kWh to 30 kWh in 2016 and again in 2019 up to 40 kWh or 62 kWh. Renault Zoe grows from 22 kWh to 41 kWh, while BMW i3 presented a first battery upgrade changing the overall battery pack from 22 kWh to 33 kWh and a second upgrade up to 42.2 kWh. b) Forecasting the fast charging infrastructure, based on the ultra-fast 450 kW chargers that allow a 42 kWh battery to recover 80% capacity in 15 minutes. Fast charging is considered essential to getting more people interested in an electric car (Neaimeh et al., 2017). But the truth is that most of the battery electric cars on the road today are incapable of charging fast (Nicholas & Hall, 2018). c) More competitive prices on the sales and after-sales markets. European Consumer Organisation (BEUC, 2016) published that ultra-low carbon electric vehicles will drop in prices substantially and they will be highly competitive, if not cheaper, than fossil fuel cars. The study forecast that in the year 2024 the average 4-year cost of running an electric vehicle should match a fossil-fuelled car. d) Reaching environmental eco-labels that allow the owners of these vehicles to drive in the city clean air zones, those restricted to the zero-emissions vehicles (Madrid Central is an example⁴). e) Achieving the “low carbon” (emissions lower to 50gCO_{2eq}/km⁵) vehicle status, helping to reach the fleet-wide average emission target for new cars (95 gCO_{2eq}/km) imposed by regulation (European Commission, 2019).

However, the automotive industry is not moving in the right direction in terms of the sustainability of transport. Despite the huge research work to improve battery properties (Kato et al, 2019; Miao et al, 2019), advances in the reduction of the specific power density (Wh/kg) are not coming on time, and batteries with high capacity still weight too much (Ding et al., 2019). Furthermore, it is not necessary to carry on a large amount of energy. Based on primary data compiled from various surveys, drivers put less than

⁴Madrid Central brochure:
www.madrid.es/UnidadesDescentralizadas/UDCMovilidadTransportes/AreaCentral/ficheros/FolletoMC.pdf

⁵ Carbon dioxide equivalency describes, for a given amount of GHG, the corresponding amount of CO₂ that would achieve the same Global Warming Potential (GWP) when it is measured over a specified timescale (100 years) (IEA. International Energy Agency, 2017)

50 km/day (Junquera et al., 2016; Pasaoglu, 2014; Wang et al., 2015). Larger batteries are planned to provide non-stop ranges for occasional uses (mainly trips to vacation spots longer distance trips) but they are not a sustainable mobility solution. The production of batteries is not growing fast enough and cannot satisfy the demand. All of the new demand from the USA, European Union and Asia is constrained at the moment by a market that remains heavily dependent on a few producers (Lebedeva et al, 2016; Gil-Alana & Monge, 2019). The market model developed by Boston Consulting Group (2019) forecasts that global capacity for battery cell production will exceed market demand by approximately 40% in 2021 and exert tremendous pressure on cell prices. However, there is an uncertainty of how the Chinese Government⁶ goals set: energy densities higher than 300 Wh/kg and costs lower than 100 €/kWh, can break the battery cell makers expectative. Battery Electric Vehicles are true zero local emissions. No Greenhouse Gas emissions exist, nor air pollutants. However, the charge of the battery with electricity from the grid causes GHG indirect emissions that must be taken into account. There exists an evident lack of cooperation between the electricity companies and the automobile industry. The commitment of electric companies is necessary for the refuelling infrastructure and forecasting of renewable energy. The characteristics of the new electric vehicles are not different from the fossil fuel models existing up to date in the market. There is not a clear diversification of efficient-in-use models. Carmakers are offering the same types of vehicles (sedan, coupe, SUV, hatchback), but powered by electricity instead of petrol or diesel. There is no evidence of a commitment to new mobility models promoted by the automobile industry.

Interest in plug-in electric vehicles is shaped primarily by consumers perceptions of electric vehicle disadvantages. There are no environmental awareness campaigns promoted by the automotive industry. In marketing campaigns, the purchase of electric vehicles (mainly hybrids) is recommended for different reasons, but not the environmental. The green or ecological company label provides for good marketing, but it is not a real aspect of the consumer's decision (Gyimesi & Viswanathan, 2011). It is complicated for potential purchasers of new cars to bet on battery electric vehicles when marketing campaigns emphasis is focused on the promotion of combustion vehicles (Broadbent et al., 2019). The electric vehicle seems more inaccessible, frivolous, and

⁶ The 13th five-year plan for economic and social development of The People's Republic of China (2016–2020) d.o. i. <http://en.ndrc.gov.cn/newsrelease/201612/P020161207645765233498.pdf>

for the use of elitist minorities and most will opt for a combustion vehicle or at most hybrid (Christidis & Focas, 2019). It is the opposite case to the introduction of mobile phones, where the customer visualized the added value (although the first mobile phones were uncomfortable). The market price of BEVs remains too high (Christidis & Focas, 2019) and many of the fully electric vehicles exceed the average sale price of an equivalent fossil-fuel vehicle model. If the trend is not broken soon, the battery electric car may finally be here, but it is still not going to be for everyone. An evolution of the powertrain based on higher battery packs does not help, because this element represents currently 70% of the price of the vehicle. Betting on a smaller number of cars with higher battery capacity versus the opposite option (lower battery energy requirement and modest range) is not a recommendable idea.

From a technological point of view, the main drawbacks are concentrated in the battery and the environmental solution could lie in a change in the mobility, with the aim in developing more BEV models (with lower ranges, specific for city use) powered with lower capacity batteries and recharged through the public and private charging infrastructure. Another possibility, already available, is to include a complementary internal combustion power plant that, burning fossil fuel, fills the batteries and helps in the vehicle traction when it is necessary. Therefore, people can drive electric cars, but in a hybrid modality that, depending on the complementary system of hybrid propulsion used, it could be defined as:

- Hybrid Electric Vehicle (HEV).
- Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV).
- Extended Range Electric Vehicle (EREV).

In a simplified manner, the differences among these three modalities are the following: HEVs (Toyota Prius, for example) include an electric motor and a motor-generator unit, producing their electricity through the combustion of fossil fuel. Vehicle traction could be electric-only, combustion motor or both at the same time. These vehicles include a lithium-ion battery with a low capacity to store energy recovered. This battery cannot charge electricity from the grid. It will be always charged through the combustion of fossil fuel in the motor-generator unit. PHEVs (Hyundai Ioniq PHEV for example) differences with HEVs are mainly that they allow charging the battery through the

electric grid and the battery capacity is far greater. Finally, EREVs (BMW i3 in example) approach is similar to BEVs (the traction is fully electric), but they include a fossil fuel motor-generator unit that helps to charge the battery, maintaining it at its best efficiency working points. In all these cases they use fossil fuel to power the vehicle and/or to recharge the battery. Even though hybrid solutions present some advantages in terms of range and refuelling, they still have one negative point in common: tailpipe emissions and their contribution to air pollution and global warming (think that today it is easier to refill fossil fuel than recharge a battery). Therefore, hybridization needs a non-local polluting actor, and this role is probably going to be assumed by hydrogen.

1.2 Hydrogen fuel cell vehicles. A future without a present?

Historically, the most extended method for obtaining hydrogen is through natural gas reforming. It is an advanced and mature production process that uses the existing natural gas pipeline delivery infrastructure. It accounts for around three-quarters of the annual global hydrogen production (70 MtH₂) being the most economical among all hydrogen production pathways (EERE, 2019). Nevertheless, this process generates 10 tons of carbon dioxide per ton of hydrogen, which results in 700Mt total CO₂ per year (IEA, 2019). Also, hydrogen is produced in large chemical plants, making it necessary to transport it to the Hydrogen Refuelling Stations (HRS) (Gallucci et al., 2006; Collodi & Wheeler, 2010) what is called off-site production. On the other hand, on-site production in HRSs would produce hydrogen utilizing water electrolysis. This method currently accounts for 2% of global hydrogen production (IEA, 2019), but it represents a significant improvement opportunity to provide low-carbon hydrogen on-site (Parra et al, 2019). This opportunity achieved in hydrogen production and storage (Turner, 2004) has encouraged some vehicle manufacturers (Hyundai, Mercedes Benz, Honda or Toyota, as examples) to develop electric vehicles powered by hydrogen fuel cells. This powertrain achieves no direct emissions as it works with a primary fuel, hydrogen, feeding a fuel cell that works as an electricity generator powering an electric motor (Abdalla et al., 2018). The system uses a low-capacity battery to recover energy (on downhill stretches and when braking kinetic energy can be stored in the battery) and providing energy when it is necessary (additional power for brisk acceleration). Tran et al., (2021) compare different alternative of range extender vehicle with the aim to find a solution to the electric vehicle range problem. In this work the authors evaluated the

advantage of use hydrogen as a fuel. In the real world the powertrains work and there exists the possibility of buying a vehicle – Toyota Mirai, Honda Clarity, Hyundai ix35 and Hyundai Nexo – with a great range as well as easy and fast charging. But, as it happens with BEVs, hydrogen-fueled vehicles will not succeed until the infrastructure necessary to support their refuelling grows. Automakers are grappling with the challenge of producing and distributing hydrogen on a large scale, but, although this is technically possible and reasonable (Cano et al., 2018), the implementation requires more time (Fernández et al., 2018; Brey et al., 2018). Therefore, it is necessary to offer solutions based on hybrid powertrains that allow to buy the vehicle and use it waiting for the development of the hydrogen refuelling infrastructure. This is not possible with current available on mass-market FCEV models, because they are fueled with hydrogen only (except the Mercedes GLC F-Cell: this plug-in fuel cell model is available in relatively small numbers and on a lease deal only). This is a chicken and egg story similar to that which is happening with the BEVs, but with the difference that the electric grid is fully developed (and the matter is focused on the battery recharge times) while the hydrogen infrastructure is, in many countries, in a preliminary development phase. It is also important not to forget that current hydrogen storage technologies have significant technical drawbacks, including the high storage pressures, but while not perfect, the current leading industry standard of compressed hydrogen offers a functional solution (Rivard et al., 2019).

The proposal here discussed is a hybrid, powered by electricity and hydrogen, that includes a plug-in battery that could achieve a moderate range between 75 and 100 km (19 kWh) and a great combined range, helped by the fuel cell system and the hydrogen stored in tanks. This hybrid configuration could be structured in three different powertrain architectures:

- **Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicle (FC-HEV):** Current fuel cell vehicles mount this powertrain. It is a vehicle that operates extracting energy from the fuel cell and including a small capacity battery (not plug-in). Both helps the fuel cell respond to the changes in speed, torque and power demanded and it also works as a buffer to store regenerative kinetic energy. This powertrain configuration does not exactly work as a hybrid because there is only one fuel (Hydrogen) and one motor (electric), nonetheless, it constitutes a similar concept to series fossil fuel hybrids (HEVs). **It is important to note that in relevant**

literature, some studies consider this powertrain as a range extender when conceptually, it is not.

- **Plug-in Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (FC-PHEV):** In the daily use of the vehicle in the city (less than 100 km, even 50 km in the more realistic scenario). Conceptually, the vehicle is powered by the electricity stored in the plug-in battery until it is exhausted. From that moment on, the fuel cell begins to produce electricity, powering the vehicle and sustaining the SoC of the battery at the minimum safety band.
- **Extended Range Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (FC-EREV):** This vehicle is powered by the electricity stored in the plug-in battery. Conceptually, the range-extender strategy controls the flow of hydrogen into the fuel cell system charging the battery, following a predefined plan aiming to improve the performance of both: the battery and the fuel cell (Fernández et al., 2016; Fernández et al., 2018) and allowing higher ranges. This powertrain architecture does not need a high-power fuel cell because the vehicle is powered by the lithium battery (Castillo et al., 2020).

Figure 1 is valid for illustrating the three above-described powertrain configurations, allowing the possibility of mounting different fuel cell stacks for different vehicle models with different power and/or different volumes of hydrogen stored in tanks when designing the powertrain, to achieve vehicle performances.

Figure 1. Extended Range/Plug-In/ Fuel Cell powertrain configuration

These hydrogen hybrid powertrains provide social-profit mobility, making it possible to put in the market a higher number of electric vehicles with lower battery packs instead of the opposite possibility. They cover greater ranges when exploring the complete propulsion possibilities: electricity and hydrogen. Currently, electrolytic hydrogen is expensive and only a few demonstration projects are supplying hydrogen from refilling stations. However, with economies of scale and technology advancements in both, renewable power and electrolysis processes, hydrogen production cost may decline from \$5/kg level today to \$1.5-2.5/kg by 2030 (Yan, 2019) boosting the hydrogen refueling infrastructure development and becoming these vehicles as real zero tailpipe emissions hybrids.

These powertrains do not emit harmful gases to the atmosphere through any tailpipe, but it is very important to determine the consumption of electricity (indirect GHG emissions source) of the following two necessary processes:

- ✓ Electricity needed for charging the plug-in battery through the electric grid.
- ✓ Electricity necessary for producing and pressurizing the hydrogen to be stored in tanks necessary to feed the fuel cell.

A Matlab-Simulink model developed for research purposes (Fernández et al., 2016; Fernández et al., 2018) will be the tool used to determine fuel consumption, emissions and range achieved by the two proposed powertrains. Therefore, it will be necessary to measure and compare their performance under impartial conditions, by means of a vehicle performance procedure identical for all.

The first contribution of this research work is to design a set of management strategies that allows to determine the range and GHG emissions of these powertrains managed following the conceptual basis rules. The second contribution lies in the proposal of a new type-approval test procedure that makes it possible to ensure which of the proposed fuel cell powertrains works best under the same conditions. Finally, the third contribution is to demonstrate the usefulness of these powertrains, which opens the door to the market introduction of such vehicles, which can operate mainly in electric mode and be feasible until the development of the future hydrogen refueling network is ready.

Our results confirm that hydrogen fuel cell range extender vehicles represent the best platform for integrating the fuel cell, allowing hydrogen to become a fuel that could play an important role in the future electrification of road transport.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 explains the background and the different methods used to determine GHG emissions, describes the limitations of the driving cycles and the proposal of approval test protocols to allow the evaluation of the hybrid hydrogen powertrains. Section 3 summarizes the methodological aspects. Section 4 displays the results of the evaluation applying different settings. These results are discussed in Section 5 and finally Section 6 reports the research findings.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Although the fuel cell technology is one of the future alternatives to completely replace the internal combustion engines, there exist studies (Zheng, 2012-a) that show that usage of hydrogen and a fuel cell as the sole energy source in a vehicle result in unmanageable costs being not an attractive solution neither for the car manufacturers nor for the consumers. Considering hybrid powertrain configurations and the problems related to hydrogen production, management and storage, it is necessary to analyze the use of hydrogen in hybrid configurations, with the purpose of removing barriers and making it more attractive to buy fuel cell vehicles. Having multiple energy sources available in the vehicle introduces new challenges regarding the way the management of energy is performed, not only for hydrogen consumption but also for the electric battery management.

Nowadays, literature provides diverse interesting research works about different techniques to supply the electric motor power demand (Dündar et al., 2020; Bubna et al., 2010), following different rule-based strategies prioritizing the load demand satisfaction (Fathy et al., 2019; Jensen et al., 2012), the reduction in emissions and hydrogen consumption (Kaya & Hames, 2019), maximizing efficiency (Liu et al., 2018; Tribioli et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2012-a; Zheng et al., 2012-b), extending the range of the fuel cell vehicles (Zeng et al., 2018) or using the lithium-ion battery and supercapacitors to provide protection to the fuel cell (Hu et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019). However, we found that there is a wide disparity in these works as to the

conceptual essence of a range extender powertrain. Furthermore, in our previous works (Fernández et al, 2016) and (Fernández et al, 2018) two hydrogen hybrid powertrain proposals were defined: a plug in and a range extender powertrain, both applied for an existing fuel cell electric vehicle already available in the market. These two powertrains were developed following the conceptual characteristics of petrol electric hybrids (Galassi et al, 2018) and determining the working conditions that will lead to better efficiency and performance of the combination of two energy sources: electricity stored in a Lithium-Ion battery and hydrogen gas in high-pressure tanks. The main configuration difference is the role of the new battery pack and its influence in vehicle performance, allowing itself a range of 100 km and being plug-in, while the hydrogen function is to recharge the battery following a predetermined strategy. From this starting point and continuing with these research works, it has been developed a set of fuel management strategies for determining the different ranges and greenhouse gas emissions for two hydrogen hybrid powertrain configurations: a Plug-In Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (FC-PHEV) and an Extended Range Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (FC-EREV). On the other hand, previous literature determined the importance of the driving conditions and driving style in the performance of ICEs (Huo et al., 2012; Pathak et al., 2016; Gallus et al., 2017; De Gennaro et al., 2014), BEVs (Álvarez et al., 2015) and hybrid electric vehicles (Al-Samari, 2017). Therefore, the performance of the fuel cell hybrid proposed powertrains should be validated using a specific type-approval test protocol in order to provide impartiality when measuring. However, currently there is not a type-approval test procedure specifically developed for fuel cell hybrids. The Worldwide Harmonized Light-duty vehicles Test Protocol (WLTP) and the Worldwide Harmonized Light-duty vehicles Test Cycle (WLTC) are applied as test approval for new passenger cars across the European Union since September 2017, succeeding the New European Driving Cycle (NEDC), which was in force since 1992. At present they find coexisting vehicles homologated with both, NEDC and WLTC, but the fuel consumption values defined in the WLTC are more realistic in sense of applying to every driver (Tsiakmakis et al., 2017; Pavlovic et al., 2016). The protocol WLTP for electric and internal combustion plug-in hybrid powertrain fuel management (ICCT, 2017) represents the steps to be followed according to in force legislation (UNECE, 2019). Consequently, as there is no specific protocol developed to test hydrogen hybrid fuel cell vehicles, the starting point is to adapt the procedure proposed for ICE hybrid vehicles. In this sense, hydrogen and fuel cell would play the role of the fossil fuel and

motor-generator unit which compose the different electric hybrid powertrain configurations.

However, all these works do not gather a complete study and comparison of fuel cell hybrid systems considering at the same time:

- The development of, not only a driving cycle, but a protocol that can be used as approval test procedure for these vehicles in the future.
- The definition of a set of rules that allow, through the simulation model, to meet the constraints of the approval test protocol, and at the same time to find the best fit of the control variables of the system.
- The development of a methodology for determining range and GHG emissions derived from the use of the different powertrain configurations, considering that these are in all cases indirect emissions.

This paper presents an impartial comparative analysis of the fuel cell powertrain architectures based in a real-world vehicle with the same set of components, but different energy flow configurations as seen in Figure 1. This analysis represents a step forward in assessing the role of hydrogen hybrid vehicles in the decarbonisation of transport.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the methodological aspects of the research work are explained. The methodology considers those relevant aspects that influence fuel consumption, range and greenhouse gas emissions of the two types of hybrid powertrains object of study. The methodology is based on three main pillars: the fuel management strategy, the approval test procedure developed and the greenhouse gas emissions calculation approach.

3.1 Overview of the simulation framework.

Figure 2 presents a schematic overview of the simulation framework developed. The powertrain components, the set of energy management rules and the type-approval test procedure are combined into a global simulation model presented in Figure 2. The complete implementation includes three main blocks:

- The **Input data generation module** manages the data that feed the model through the variables that define the two hybrid vehicles: drive cycle, high and low SoC limits and battery recharge current.
- The **Approval test procedure module** imposes the constraints that conducts the simulation following the mandates of the approval test.
- The **Vehicle simulation block** includes the information of the vehicle dynamics (size, weight, drag coefficient...), powertrain information (motor, inverters, battery and fuel cell, hydrogen and electricity available) and the energy management rules designed.

The input data generation module supplies the drive cycle, the value for establishing the constraints forming the SoC band and an initial value of the battery charging current. With these values, a set of simulations will be conducted varying the value of the battery charging current. The resulting ranges obtained from each run are automatically stored. After finishing the first set of simulations, the iterative procedure selects a new pair of SoC values and repeats the procedure. As far as greenhouse gas emissions are concerned, the calculation is done only once, as the amount of stored energy is the same in each of the different hybrid vehicles.

Figure 2. Working flow of the proposed simulation framework.

Below we present the most important methodological basis necessary to understand the model developed.

3.2 Fuel management rule strategy

Depending on the type of fuel cell hybrid vehicle, the powertrain presents different behaviors to meet the functionality requirements as well as increase the range of the vehicle among other constraints. Each of the two proposed fuel cell hybrid powertrains is equipped with a plug-in battery and a fuel cell that converts hydrogen into electricity. Two main operating modes that characterize fuel management are considered:

1. The Charge Depleting mode (CD), which is the mode that allows the Li-ion battery to be discharged when it is powering the electric motor.

2. The Charge Sustaining mode (CS), when the fuel cell operates to either help to power the vehicle and/or charging the battery.

In this work, a simulation environment is developed (see Figure 2), which allows simulating both, a plug-in and a range extender powertrain. The battery equipped in the vehicle works between two values of State of Charge (SoC) following a test procedure (WLTP). The simulation model allows to determine the range with different SoC minimum and maximum values and applying different power supplied by the fuel cell. The current management block (CMB) distributes the current demanded by the electric motor (I_d) using a series of management rules that configure the block to meet the constraints established. Specifically, using these systematic rules, the CMB (see Figure 3) computes the part of demanded current that would be supplied by the battery (I_{Bat}) and the part supplied by the fuel cell (I_{Fc}) at any moment and for the different working conditions. The decision is done depending on the specific conditions defined by the set of rules.

The inputs are the battery SoC, the hydrogen tank level (LH_2), the current demanded by the motor (I_d) and the current that the fuel cell provides to recharge the battery (I_{Fcr}). The output results are the range and GHG emissions (CO_{2eq}). One of the constraints for CMB operation is to keep the battery SoC within the desired range and to use the hydrogen efficiently. The current demanded by the electric motor plays an important role within the operation of the rules, that is, depending on its value, the current will be supplied by the battery, by the fuel cell or by both. In the case that the vehicle supports regenerative braking, the current would be used to recharge the battery.

Figure 3. System Block Structure

A rule-based strategy usually does not require knowledge of future operating conditions because the rules are based on intuition and experience. This type of control strategy is widely used in hybrid vehicles, owing to its simplicity and practicability. In this research work, the proposed current distribution rules behavior have been detailed in Figure 4. These control rules are applied to the range extender and plug-in configuration powertrains, respectively. The rules generate six different outputs, each one implies a different distribution strategy for the battery and the fuel cell operations. Specifically, in **output 1** the vehicle operates in charge depleting mode, considering that the battery SoC is above its minimum pre-established value (SoC_{min}). In this case, the battery supplies the full power to the electric motor. This mode is used until this predefined minimum SoC level is reached. Note that, whenever the system allows for regenerative braking, or during downhill, the CMB sets a recharge current for the time the condition holds (**output 2**).

Figure 4. Control distribution rules

Output 3 corresponds to sustaining mode. This occurs when the battery SoC reaches the minimum SoC level and the hydrogen in the tank is then used by the CMB. Under this condition, the fuel cell supplies the current demanded by the electric motor plus a (configurable) battery charge current I_{FC} . The system keeps the charge sustaining mode until a (configurable) maximum SoC level (SoC_{max}) is reached. The recharge current, I_{FCr} , is selected after a previous sweep through different current values, selecting the one that can properly charge the battery and, at the same time, extending the range of the vehicle. **Outputs 4, 5 and 6** are established to guarantee the good performance for the vehicle, without risks for the components involved. Specifically, the maximum current

supplied by the fuel cell and the one corresponding to the battery has been selected to ensure a safety current distribution (avoiding exceeding the current SoC limits) and, at the same time, reducing the risk of overcharge. If the current demanded by the motor is higher than the capability of the battery and the fuel cell, those are limited to supply their maximum established values. On the other hand, if the current demanded only exceeds the fuel-cell capability, then the battery will supply the current in excess, while the fuel cell is used at its maximum capability. Finally, the system enters in a “stop” mode when it gets out of fuel (example: when the hydrogen tank goes empty and the battery SoC reaches 10 %).

The Plug-in and the Range Extender powertrains conceptual differences are explained as follows:

- The **Plug-In** is set to discharge the lithium battery until it reaches a specific minimum SoC value. From this moment on, the fuel cell provides power to drive the vehicle, sustaining the battery SoC until reaching destination. The lower battery SoC allowed is usually 20%, therefore the fuel cell must sustain the battery within a safety band of SoC and power the motor, avoiding battery discharging below that critical value.
- The **Range Extender** is set to sustain the battery within a SoC band searching for improving battery efficiency. In this sense, the lithium battery is discharged until a specific value of State of Charge (low position), and then the fuel cell starts working supplying power, charging the battery and powering the motor until the battery reaches the high position of the band of SoC. This procedure is repeated, keeping the battery between the two specific values, trying that both, battery and fuel cell, operate with high efficiency.

3.3 Type approval test procedure

As the objective of this research is to compare the powertrain fuel management, a test protocol that considers the characteristics of FC-PHEVs and FC-EREVs is necessary. Specifically, the way to compute the range and GHG emissions is addressed following a concrete procedure. Each control strategy is applied, and the consumption of both fuels are evaluated, the electricity stored in the battery and the hydrogen in tanks, analyzing

the vehicle range and greenhouse gas emissions ($\text{CO}_{2\text{eq}}$) following a standardized procedure. ~~The Worldwide Harmonized Light-duty vehicles Test Protocol (WLTP) and the Worldwide Harmonized Light-duty vehicles Test Cycle (WLTC) for calculating consumptions are applied as test approval for new passenger cars across the European Union since September 2017, succeeding the New European Driving Cycle (NEDC), which was in force since 1992. At present they find coexisting hybrid (fossil fuel and electricity) vehicles homologated with both, NEDC and WLTC, but the fuel consumption values determined in the WLTC are more realistic in sense of applying to every driver (Tsiakmakis et al., 2017; Pavlovic et al., 2016).~~

Figure 5. Schematic overview of the test procedure for extended range and plug-in hydrogen hybrids. Adapted from ICCT (2017)

~~The protocol WLTP for electric and internal combustion plug-in hybrid powertrain fuel management (ICCT, 2017) represents the steps to be followed according to in force Regulation N° 101 (UN ECE R101) of the Economic Commission for Europe of the United Nations (UNECE, 2019). It begins with a battery fully charged, and the vehicle will be mainly driven using the electric battery, except if the power demand makes necessary the internal combustion engine assist. When the battery is depleted, the vehicle will use the Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) for driving and the battery can still be used for storing recovered energy from regenerative braking, but it will generally remain at about the same charge level.~~

~~There is no specific protocol to test hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, therefore the nearest are those proposed for ICE hybrid vehicles (ICCT, 2017). In this sense, hydrogen and fuel cell plays the role of the fossil fuel and motor-generator unit which forms the PHEV powertrain.~~

Starting from the ICE hybrid vehicles test basis, we have adapted this test to fuel cell hybrid vehicles presenting the following phases (see Figure 5):

- **Phase 1: Battery Depleting.** After being charged the battery up to its maximum SoC in a controlled environment (23°C), the vehicle is tested over multiple WLTCs till a predetermined low level of battery SoC is reached.
- **Phase 2: Battery Sustaining for FC-PHEVs.** After the battery reaches the low level of SoC (in this case corresponds to a value near the minimum SoC allowed by the battery), in this second phase the system keeps the SoC level. In the case of FC-PHEVs, the battery SoC must be sustained within the margins of a safety band using electricity supplied by the fuel cell that charges the battery and feeds the motor. As the priority is to save hydrogen, when the battery reaches the top of the safety band, it will begin to discharge till its SoC falls below the lower limit of the band again.
- **Phase 2: Battery sustaining for FC-EREVs.** In this case, **Phase 1** would finish earlier (at a medium SoC value) and during **Phase 2** the battery SoC is sustained within the margins of an improvement efficiency band using electricity supplied by the fuel cell that charges the battery and feeds the motor. This sustaining band is similar to the one included in the case of FC-PHEVs but centered to a medium value of battery SoC.
- **Phase 3:** The duration of the test is limited to the exhaustion of both fuels. When the hydrogen tanks had been completely emptied, the management system will begin depleting the battery till finish the test when SoC reaches its lowest limit admissible (10%). The maximum and minimum SoC values are set at 90% and 10% respectively for deep discharge protection.

3.4 GHG emissions calculation procedure

The emissions (indirect) of these bi-fuel powertrains must be calculated as a sum of their respective emissions in the use of the vehicle following the described type-approval test. This test involves the consumption of all the fuel stored, consequently the value of greenhouse gas emissions will be the same in any of the strategies. It is therefore the range that determines a higher or lower value for emissions per kilometer driven. In the case of the electricity stored in the battery, it must be considered the Electricity Emission Factor ⁷ of the country where the vehicle is charged. In the case of hydrogen emissions, it will be calculated the energy necessary to charge the tanks of the vehicle with hydrogen produced in situ at a filling station through water electrolysis.

- **Emissions due to battery charging**

The emissions from electricity consumption are determined by applying an emission factor that represents the emissions (in gCO_{2eq}) that the mix of electricity sources of the country where the vehicle is charged produces per kWh generated. Country-specific emission factors for grid electricity are usually published. In this sense, Electricity Map⁸ represents a live visualization of where electricity comes from and how much CO_{2eq} is emitted.

- **Emissions due to hydrogen supply**

To evaluate GHG emissions associated with the process of filling up the tanks with H₂ fuel compressed at 700 bars, it will be necessary a source of hydrogen as well as a system for pressurizing it. It must be considered the energy consumption during these two phases: production and pressurization.

~~Beginning with the source of hydrogen, the most extended method for obtaining it is through natural gas reforming. It is an advanced and mature production process that uses the existing natural gas pipeline delivery infrastructure. It accounts for around three quarters of the annual global hydrogen production (70 Mth₂) being the most economical among all hydrogen production pathways~~

⁷ Measure of CO_{2eq} emissions intensity per unit of electricity generation in the grid system.

⁸ <https://www.electricitymap.org>

(EERE, 2019). Nevertheless, this process generates carbon monoxide that contaminates the hydrogen produced and this dependence on fossil fuels generates 10 tons of carbon dioxide per ton of hydrogen, which results in 700Mt total CO₂ per year (IEA, 2019). Also, hydrogen is produced in large chemical plants, making it necessary to transport it to the Hydrogen Refuelling Stations (HRS) (Gallucci et al., 2006; Colodi & Wheeler, 2010) what is called off-site production. On the other hand, on-site production in HRSs would produce hydrogen utilizing water electrolysis. This method currently accounts for 2% of global hydrogen production (IEA, 2019), but it represents a significant improvement opportunity to provide low-carbon hydrogen on-site (Parra et al., 2019). Two methods are distinguished for electrolysis: traditional room-temperature and high temperature. The last one is particularly interesting when there is a source next and it is more attractive, in economic terms than room-temperature electrolysis (Hurtado & Soria, 2007) because the process achieves less electricity consumption. There remains, however, the problem of transportation. Electrolysis at room temperature allows producing hydrogen on-site, being this its main advantage, because, on the contrary, commercial electrolyze systems achieve poor efficiency range 60-70% (Davidson et al., 2017; Genovese et al., 2020). The electric energy required is 285.8 kJ per mole, following the chemical reaction $2\text{H}_2\text{O} + e^- \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$ at one atmosphere of pressure and 25° Celsius, it accounts 40 kWh/kgH₂. Nevertheless, due to the efficiency, the final consumption is up to 65 kWh/kgH₂ (Harrison et al., 2010). Commercial PEM electrolyzers produce hydrogen at a pression of 30 bars with an electric efficiency of 58 kWh/kgH₂ (IRENA, 2018).

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of the general HRS component configuration

Hydrogen is stored at HRSs in tanks and pressurized up to 700 bar when refuelling the vehicle (see Figure 6). Datasheet of Hyundai Fuel-Cell vehicle

shows that a total hydrogen mass of 5.64 kg is stored distributed into two tanks with 37l and 103l capacity. Therefore, the only variable unknown is the temperature, which can be calculated using the Van der Waals' law (Equation 1) (Moran et al., 2010):

$$\left[P + a \cdot \left(\frac{n}{V} \right)^2 \right] \cdot \left(\frac{V}{n} - b \right) = R \cdot T \quad [1]$$

Where:

P = pressure (700 bar).

V = volume (140 l).

n = number of moles (5.64 kg H₂ → 3140 moles).

R = hydrogen gas constant (8.33048 J/(K·mole)).

T = temperature (Kelvin).

a = measure of attraction between particles (0.02476 (J·m³)/mole²).

b = volume excluded by a mole of particles (2.661·10⁻⁵ (J·m³)/(mole²)).

Temperature is then calculated, resulting in approximately 223K (-50°C). With these data is possible to find that 2.16 kWh (6.5% of minimum inferior calorific value 120MJ/kgH₂) are needed to compress 1 kg H₂ from ambient pressure (1.01 bar) to tank storage pressure (700 bar). It should be noted that energy consumption is calculated for reversible isothermal compressions, the actual consumption is slightly higher. Thus, the energy consumption needed will be between 6% and 10% of the lower calorific value of hydrogen (Hurtado & Soria, 2007). Furthermore, empirical results published (Brown & Samuelsen, 2012) show that electricity consumption including even the station lighting is 5.18 kWh per kg of hydrogen dispensed. Therefore, the global energy necessary to produce and pressurize 1 kg H₂ is 70 kWh in the worst-case scenario.

~~3.4 Summary of the methodology: Overview of the simulation process.~~

~~Earlier the powertrain components, the set of energy management rules and the type approval test procedure were explained. These subparts are combined into the global simulation model shown in Figure 6. The complete implementation includes three main blocks:~~

- ~~The **Input data generation module** manages the data that feed the model through the variables that define the two hybrid vehicles: drive cycle, high and low SoC limits and battery recharge current.~~
- ~~The **Approval test procedure module** imposes the constraints that conducts the simulation following the mandates of the approval test.~~
- ~~The **Vehicle simulation block** includes the information of the vehicle dynamics (size, weight, drag coefficient...), powertrain information (motor, inverters, battery and fuel cell, hydrogen and electricity available) and the energy management rules designed.~~

~~The input data generation module supplies the drive cycle, the value for establishing the constraints forming the SoC band and an initial value of the battery charging current. With these values a set of simulations are conducted varying the value of the battery charging current. The resulting ranges obtained from each run is automatically stored. After finishing the first set of simulations, the iterative procedure selects a new pair of SoC values and repeats the procedure with all the SoC intervals proposed and the recharge currents selected. As far as greenhouse gas emissions are concerned, the calculation is done only once, as the amount of stored energy is the same in each of the different hybrid vehicles.~~

~~Figure 6. Working flow of the proposed simulation framework.~~

4 RESULTS

In this section, we summarize the results obtained by applying the proposed methodology to the powertrain configurations (FC-PHEV and FC-EREV), determining the range and the emissions per km.

4.1 Simulation environment data

In this sub-section, it is explained the specific powertrain model developed with Simulink software. This block set series allow modelling, in a unique simulation environment, the electrical and mechanical systems. Unless specifically indicated, we will use for the evaluation the vehicle configuration data (Table 1) extracted from the Hyundai ix35 Fuel Cell. This vehicle uses a 100 kW (134 horsepower) squirrel cage induction motor that offers constant maximum torque of 300 Nm (0-3600 rpm) and constant power of 100 kW (3600-7200 rpm).

Overall Length (mm)	4410
Overall Width (mm)	1820
Overall Height (mm)	1650
Wheelbase (mm)	2640
Front Wheel Tread (mm)	1585
Rear Wheel Tread (mm)	1586
Front Over Hang (mm)	880
Rear Over Hang (mm)	890
Cargo Area (VDA) (liter)	551
Lightest Curb Weight (kg)	2250
Heaviest Curb Weight (kg)	2290
Gross Vehicle Weight (kg)	2290

Table 1. *Vehicle dynamics*⁹

The characteristics of the battery for FC-EREVs and FC-PHEVs are summarized in Table 2. This battery must achieve a range value of around 100 km driving in CD battery mode only.

Energy content	19 kWh
Capacity (per cell)	50 Ah
Voltage	380 V
Discharge cont. (power)	200 A (80 kW)
Discharge peak. (power)	400 A (160 kW)
Max charging current	80 A

Table 2. *Battery parameters (Fernández et al., 2018)*

A fuel cell technology with ideal characteristics for road vehicle applications is the Proton Exchange Membrane (PEMFC). It has high overall efficiency, quick start-up, low-temperature operation a long lifetime, small volume, less weight and non-corrosive features (Bromaghim et al, 2010). It is modelled following textbook procedures (Pukrushpan et al, 2002; Wang, 2004; Dio et al, 2008). Its voltage range is 250 V to 450 V, 100 kW of power and composed of 440 cells assembled in lamination. The vehicle includes 5.64 kg of hydrogen pressured at 700 bar.

4.2 Powertrain proposals analysis

⁹ Automobile-catalogue. Hyundai ix35 Fuel Cell specifications: versions & types. https://www.automobile-catalog.com/model/hyundai/ix35_fuel_cell.html

With the focus put on analyzing the powertrain proposals, we conducted a series of simulations applying the type-approval test procedure.

- **Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicle (FC-HEV) powertrain results**

First, the fuel cell hybrid electric is tested. The battery proposed in this article is removed and the fuel cell works alone, supplying the current demanded by the electric motor. Normally, this kind of powertrain needs a small battery to help the fuel cell when the current demanded by the electric motor is very high, not for improving range or emissions. In this case, the fuel cell can supply the whole current demanded. To determine the range for this powertrain the drive cycle WLTC class 2 and class 3 are used. Results are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Hydrogen tank level (FC-HEV) by applying WLTC class 2(right) and class 3(left).

- **Extended Range Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (FC-EREV) powertrain results**

To apply the rules designed, a set of intervals for the maximum and minimum SoC values are defined in order to find the best interval for the range extender configuration. The interval selected will offer the greater range that the vehicle can travel with this configuration. For each interval, different values for fuel cell current (I_{FCr}) are used to recharge the battery when it reaches the minimum established SoC. It is important to remark that I_{FCr} must not exceed the maximum battery recharge current (80A, as seen in Table 2). I_{FCr} values used range from 5 to 80 A. Each simulation was set to run by applying consecutive WLTCs class 3 driving cycles and following the approval test procedure. The

results of these simulations are displayed in Table 3. It should be noted that Table 3 resumes the best I_{Fcr} values for each one of the SoC intervals proposed.

<i>SoC (%)</i>	25- 35	25- 45	25- 55	25- 65	25- 75	35- 65	35- 45	35- 55	45- 55	45- 65	45- 75	55- 65	55- 75	55- 85	65- 75
<i>Range (km)</i>	530	531	531	531	531	520	520	520	508	508	508	499	499	499	487
<i>I_{Fcr} (A)</i>	25	60	45	80	20	20	30	30	50	40	75	40	55	80	20

Table 3. WLTC class 3 simulation results

Based on the results presented in Table 3, and aiming to maximize the range of the vehicle, it is recommended to discharge the battery until 25% SoC before starting the work of the fuel cell. Though the results for 25% of minimum SoC are similar, sustained band intervals starting in 25 % presents the best results for this configuration.

Once it is set the best interval for the range extender powertrain, the next step is to let it work under extreme conditions, and thus, get the greatest range that the vehicle can travel with the selected interval and recharge current presented in Table 3. For this experiment, the simulation run until the hydrogen tank is empty and the battery is discharged until 10% of SoC once the hydrogen is over. Results of this simulation displayed in Figure 8 show the battery SoC (left) and the remaining percentage of the hydrogen tank level (right). As can be deduced, the battery starts with 90% of capacity and then, when the vehicle starts to move, the charge depleting mode begins until the SoC level reaches 25%. After that, the charge sustaining mode starts, which means that the battery is recharged by the fuel cell with a constant current of 60 A until 45% of SoC is reached. The process is repeated alternatively, according to the programmed rules. Then, when the hydrogen is over, the battery continues supplying energy to the motor until the battery SoC reaches 10%. In Figure 8 (right) it is possible to see how the hydrogen tank starts full and then how it is discharged until it is empty. It can be noted how the system alternates between battery depleting and sustaining modes, matching the battery behavior. The simulation is set to run by applying consecutive WLTC class 3 driving cycles, covering a total of 28.37 cycles, corresponding to 23.26 km each, therefore the total range is 660 km. The

simulation finishes when it is not possible to recharge the battery because the hydrogen tank is empty and the battery SoC level drops till 10%.

Figure 8. Battery SoC and hydrogen tank level variations by applying WLTC class 3 to FC-EREV.

To complete the results of the type-approval test proposed in this article, the rules designed are applied to the CMB using a different drive cycle. This experiment aims to cover different vehicles. In this case, we selected the drive cycle WLTC class 2. This drive cycle is used for vehicles of $34 \geq \text{PMR} > 22$ (PMR parameter is defined as the ratio of rated power (W) and the curb mass (kg)). The best intervals for the range extender configuration are determined by applying the same procedure explained for the WLTC class 3 with I_{Fcr} values range from 5 to 20 A. Table 4 shows the results of the range found for each interval.

<i>SoC (%)</i>	25-35	25-45	25-55	25-65	25-75	35-65	35-45	35-55	45-55	45-65	45-75	55-65	55-75	55-85	65-75
<i>Range (km)</i>	665	665	665	665	665	652	652	652	638	638	638	625	625	625	612
<i>I_{Fcr} (A)</i>	10	5	5	5	5	5	10	5	10	5	5	10	5	20	10

Table 4. WLTC class 2 simulation results

The results presented in Table 4 show that the best option to achieve more range is to discharge the battery till 25% SoC, start the sustaining mode charging the battery up to 45% SoC. In this mode it is applied a constant recharge current (I_{Fcr}) of 5A. Figure 9 shows the results of applying consecutively WLTC class 2 until the hydrogen tank is empty and the battery SoC level reaches 10% of capacity. The simulation is configured to run by applying WLTCs class 2,

covering 56.61 cycles, each cycle corresponding to 14.66 km. Under this condition and setting 5A of recharge current (I_{Fcr}), when the battery is in charge sustaining mode, the vehicle covers 830 km.

Figure 9. Battery SoC and hydrogen tank level variations by applying WLTC class 2 to a FC-EREV.

- **Plug-in Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle powertrain**

To validate the plug-in powertrain configuration, we set different values for the recharge current (I_{Fcr}) following the approval test procedure. The vehicle starts with 90% SoC and the battery is used to power the electric motor continuously until the SoC level reaches 20%. After that, the fuel cell starts to supply a recharge current (I_{Fcr}) to keep the battery SoC around 20%. The goal of this configuration is to save hydrogen.

It is important to note that although this power train configuration aims to keep the level of SoC around 20%, for real vehicles, this small interval could compromise the battery and fuel cell life. To avoid this, it is proposed to set a 5% SoC interval, to guarantee a good performance without inducing damage risks to the components. Different I_{Fcr} values, ranging from 5 to 80 A are tried. Each simulation was set by applying consecutive WLTCs class 3. Despite that, the simulation stops when the hydrogen tank is empty and SoC reaches 10% after the hydrogen is over. Found that the best recharge current corresponds to 50 A, ensuring the highest range. Specifically, using this recharge current, the vehicle can travel 661 km. The results for this configuration are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Battery SoC (left) and hydrogen tank level variations (right) applying WLTC class 3 to a FC-PHEV.

From Figure 10 (left), it is possible to see the intervals for the battery SoC, once it reaches 20% of capacity. The drive cycle class 2 is tested for plug-in configuration too. Simulations show that using 5A (I_{FCr}), the vehicle can travel 828 km. This experiment is made until the hydrogen tank is empty and SoC reaches 10% after the hydrogen is over. Figure 11 shows the state of charge (SoC) and the hydrogen tank level for this configuration.

Figure 11. Battery SoC (left) and hydrogen tank level variations (right) applying WLTC class 2 to FC-PHEV

- **Current management strategy performance**

Now, it will be compared the performance of the CMB and the strategy proposed in our previous work (Fernández et al., 2016), where four different

current values were selected to recharge the battery using the fuel cell (20, 40 and 80 A respectively) and only one SoC interval that covers from 30% to 80%. To perform the comparison, a set up new is proposed with the desired SoC interval and sweeping through the different current values to find the best recharge current (I_{Fcr}) for the selected interval. It is found that the best I_{Fcr} value for the SoC interval is 55 A. Results of the comparison are shown in Figure 12. The proposals in (Fernández et al., 2016) considers that for a small current (20 A) it is not possible to complete the charge of the battery even though there is hydrogen in the tank, while on the other hand, for 40A and 80A, the fuel cell can recharge the battery, achieving ranges of 500 km and 530 km respectively. The new proposal outperforms the results with the same SoC interval and providing 55 A. Using this configuration, the vehicle can achieve 660 km. WLTC class 3 was applied for both current managements until the hydrogen tank is over and then the battery SoC level drops and reaches 10%.

Figure 12. SoC depleting & sustaining mode by applying different control strategies

4.3 Summary of results

Global results obtained corresponding to the different configurations of the powertrain are summarized in Table 5. The vehicle stores 19 kWh in the battery pack and 5.64 kg of hydrogen. To evaluate the consumptions and GHG emissions for a combined global range, it is necessary to consider that the battery uses 80% of global SoC (15 kWh) and the whole hydrogen stored, which implies 395 kWh of energy consumption. Therefore, energizing the vehicle implies an electricity consumption of 410 kWh.

Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicle					
Drive cycle	Global range (km)	Energy Consumption (Wh/km)	H ₂ Consumption (kgH ₂ /100km)	CO ₂ emissions Spain (gCO ₂ /km)	CO ₂ emissions Poland (gCO ₂ /km)
Class 2	582	678	0.96	128	503
Class 3	464	850	1.21	161	631
Plug-in Fuel Cell Hybrid					
Class 2	828	493	0.68	94	357
Class 3	661	617	0.85	117	447
Extended Range Fuel Cell Hybrid					
Class 2	830	492	0.68	93	356
Class 3	665	613	0.85	116	444

Table 5. Summary of results for different hybridization configurations until fuels (electricity and hydrogen) are exhausted.

5 DISCUSSION

At the conceptual level, we have reaffirmed the role of hybridization as fundamental to achieving range extension in fuel cell vehicles by incorporating a lithium-ion battery into the powertrain topology and applying rules to improve overall vehicle range, efficiency or GHG emissions. However, the specific conceptual range-extender powertrain that arises from hybrid petrol-electric vehicles is the one applied in this research article. On the other hand, the approval test procedure applied to perform the simulations is one of the novelties of our research. The comparison with the works published by other authors has been rather difficult because the vehicle performance is different (neither better nor worse) and the results obtained will be different. In this sense, in this discussion section we will analyze the validity of the results presented by comparing to other similar real-world vehicles as well as to the models and algorithms used in the simulations in the literature.

Analyzing Table 5, it can be seen the different functionalities of hydrogen-powered vehicles, their range, fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Both WLTC class 2 and class 3 type-approval test cycles have been included because this vehicle could be used for passengers and for last-mile delivery. A first overview of the results shows that both (FC-EREV and FC-PHEV) powertrain proposals achieve better fuel

management than the current fuel cell powertrain configuration. The addition of a battery with 19 kWh energy storage does not only make it possible to drive 100 km more but also increases the efficiency of the whole system achieving higher ranges. It is possible to see that the best management performance obtained with the range extender configuration is very similar to that achieved with the plug-in configuration.

Concerning hydrogen consumption, data presented in Table 5 (kgH₂/100km) depends on the powertrain configuration selected. It is around 0.85 kgH₂/100km for extender range and plug-in powertrains applying WLTC class 3 type-approval test procedure. This value is consistent as compared to Wu et al., (2019) proposal of intelligent vehicles or Song et al. (2021) that achieves a consumption range of 0.76 kg/100 km and 1.26 kg/100 km. (Geng et al., 2019) proposal of a range extender control strategy for commercial vehicles achieves the best hydrogen consumption depending on the initial SoC of the battery (2.40 kg/100 km with an initial SoC of 80% and 2.95 kg/100 km with an initial SoC of 50%), both higher than the hydrogen consumption achieved by the here presented simulations, 1.14 kg/100 km, which largely improves the proposal. According to real-world hydrogen hybrid consumptions: Renault Kangoo ZE I Grand Volume (0.87 kgH₂/100km)¹⁰, Mercedes-Benz GLC F-CELL (0.97 kgH₂/100km)¹¹ or the new SUV Hyundai Nexo (0.84 kgH₂/100km)¹². On the other hand, emissions comparative with current ICE hybrids as Hyundai Ioniq (85g CO₂/km)¹³ or Toyota RAV4 (133 gCO₂/km)¹⁴ reveals that it is quite important the country where the vehicle is charged and its electricity mix. In France or in Spain, the emissions are lower than ICE hybrids with the same characteristics, however, in Poland, the opposite occurs, and the emissions expected are higher than those generated by ICE hybrids. This reinforces, even more, the messages relating to the best and quickest development of alternatives based on the use of renewable energies. Results reveal that the comparative with equivalent BEV powertrains that could achieve this range (near 660 km), it would be

¹⁰ <https://h2.live/en/wasserstoffautos/kangoo-ze-h2>

¹¹ <https://h2.live/en/wasserstoffautos/mercedes-glc>

¹² <https://h2.live/en/wasserstoffautos/hyundai-nexo>

¹³ <https://www.evspecifications.com/en/model/f21a6d>

¹⁴ <https://www.toyota.es/coches/rav4/>

necessary to integrate a battery seven times higher in energy storage (133 kWh). This would result in a vehicle weight up to 650 kg as a function of the energy densities of any battery technology in the market (200-265 Wh/kg) (Ulvestad, 2018). Comparative with the original powertrain fuel cell vehicle ix35 (achieving a NEDC range of 594 km) it would be necessary to include 35% more hydrogen stored in the vehicle to increase the range. This confirms that control rules designed for the management strategy block applied to both proposed hybrid powertrains (FC-EREV and FC-PHEV) allow driving 660 km using the driving cycle WLTC class 3 and 830 km using WLTC class 2 test, respectively. The control rules designed to probe that is possible not to increase the range when it is compared with current fuel cell vehicles.

The results obtained for the different intervals to find the best range extender configuration show that the vehicle has a better performance when the battery is discharged to lower levels of SoC. In this sense, it is possible to increase the range when the battery SoC level drops to 25 % - 35 % before starting its recharge by the fuel cell.

It is important to remark that the fuel cell used is capable to supply 220 A of maximum current and that the demand profiles never exceed 130 A. This means that the proposed powertrain sizing can supply the current demanded by the electric motor without overloading, however, the control rules were designed to achieve the best system performance. Note that the main shortcoming of hybrid vehicles is that they are oversized in powertrains. This leads to a new research specifically on this aspect and the strategy to be considered to implement more and different rules.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The future of mobility inevitably involves the hybridization of fuels in the near term to ensure long-term mobility sustainability solutions. Currently, the state of the situation is that there are not powertrains that include all the features that are highly demanded from car users (higher ranges, lower charging times, reasonable prize and development of refuelling infrastructure) and governments (zero direct tailpipe pollution and minimum GHG emissions). BEVs, HEVs and PHEVs features do not meet all the needs and expectations of their potential users. In the present paper, it has been analyzed the possibilities of hybridization with hydrogen to open the door to a better

accomplishment, as the configurations of powertrain presented do not emit direct pollutant gas and only generate indirect emissions. It has been presented a method to evaluate the range, fuel consumption and emissions based on a variation on the current test used to homologate ICE hybrids. The conclusions of this research could be summarized in the following findings:

Test procedure: It has been developed a test procedure that allows a fair simulation-based comparison between the powertrains analyzed. In the absence of a specific procedure for fuel cell hybrid vehicles, a new one has been developed based on those already existing for internal combustion hybrids.

Fuel cell powertrains viability: The objectives have been attained. Starting from an available in the market fuel cell vehicle, a set of powertrain management proposals based on two hydrogen hybrid powertrains (plugin and extended range), including a 19 kWh battery, have been analyzed and the goals proposed have been achieved. Both powertrains would be useful today pending the development of a hydrogen refuelling network. Extended Range Fuel Cell Hybrid is the best option, with higher range and lowest GHG emissions.

Environmental benefits: The vehicle achieves zero local emissions and moderate indirect GHG emissions (lower than fossil fuel current similar vehicles). However, these indirect emissions are linked to the emission factor of each country. Those countries with greater reliance on coal will achieve important improvements in air quality but may not always be sufficient to reach the objective in GHG indirect emissions.

Comparative with current BEVs and FCVs: Concerning BEVs, a powertrain with an equivalent range would be a priori less pollutant. However, it would be necessary to increase the battery to a level of storage that would worsen the situation rather than improve it in two technical aspects (charging time and vehicle mass) and in a mobility ethical aspect (with this battery capacity it could be possible to feed ten lighter BEVs with a 50 km range, ideal for getting around the city). Concerning the proposed fuel cell vehicle, the range could be improved by including more hydrogen, nevertheless, the basic problem of this

vehicle with only hydrogen as fuel will still being the lack of existing refuelling infrastructure.

Note that the main shortcoming of this type of vehicles known as hybrids, and that the oversized powertrain leads to very high values for the power of the two engines. This gives way to a new research specifically on this aspect and the strategy to be considered to implement more and different rules. In this case, both the battery and the fuel cell can provide all the power demanded by the engine.

As a final remark, the authors hope that this work will contribute to shed light and reflect on alternatives that might contribute to the responsible use of technologies and fuels towards the decarbonization of transport. Hydrogen production with electricity obtained from renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind energy, could be the definitive impulse to a real non-polluting electric mobility.

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